

ICSU World Data System Annual Report 2012–13

Prepared by the WDS International Programme Office

Trusted data services
for global science

ICSU World Data System
Annual Report 2012–13

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‘WDS supports ICSU’s mission and objectives, ensuring the long-term stewardship and provision of quality-assessed data and data services to the international science community and other stakeholders.’

Strategic Committee on Information and Data Report, ICSU 2008

WDS Goals

- Enable universal and equitable access to quality-assured scientific data, data services, products and information.
- Ensure long-term data stewardship.
- Foster compliance to agreed-upon data standards and conventions.
- Provide mechanisms to facilitate and improve access to data and data products.

Introduction

The ICSU World Data System (ICSU-WDS) was created by the 29th General Assembly of the International Council for Science (ICSU) and builds on the 50-year legacy of the former ICSU World Data Centres and Federation of Astronomical and Geophysical data-analysis Services with the aim of transitioning from standalone components to a common globally coordinated and distributed data system.

By ensuring universal and equitable access to, and long-term stewardship of, quality-assured scientific data and data services, products, and information covering a broad range of natural sciences and expanding to social sciences, WDS supports ICSU's mission of 'strengthening international science for the benefit of society'.

2012–2013 in Brief

May 2012 saw ICSU-WDS open its new International Programme Office (WDS-IPO) in an official ceremony in Tokyo, Japan. Hosted by the National Institute of Information and Communications Technology, the WDS-IPO manages the operations of ICSU-WDS under the guidance of the second WDS Scientific Committee (WDS-SC) appointed in June by the Executive Board of the International Council for Science (ICSU-EB). Fresh insight was brought to ICSU-WDS, whilst ensuring continuity, by replacing half of the WDS-SC and inviting the remainder to serve a second term (2012–2015). In response to ICSU's research priorities, the ICSU-EB also decided to exceptionally establish a thirteenth seat to cover the Health Sciences.

The new WDS-SC has been tasked with positioning ICSU-WDS as the *premium global multidisciplinary network for quality-assessed scientific data* so that significant contributions can be made to projects such as Future Earth. ICSU-WDS will

thus provide several essential leading-edge services, including a community-based Data Publication and Curation Service, and an Open Metadata Catalogue and Scalable Knowledge Network. WDS Working Groups launched in 2013 will realize prototype implementations of these services.

Finally, ICSU-WDS continued to strengthen its ties with the Committee on Data for Science and Technology (CODATA) in 2012–2013. The two organizations jointly coordinated sessions at the Planet under Pressure 2012 Conference (27 March 2012; London, United Kingdom), Rio+20 Forum on Science, Technology and Innovation for Sustainable Development (14 June 2012, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil), as well as the Future Earth Stakeholders' Workshop (29 November 2012; Paris, France). The bonds between ICSU-WDS and CODATA will be further reinforced in the coming years following the landmark decision to co-host joint WDS–CODATA Conferences from 2014.

‘The World Data System vision is to transform today’s collection of data bodies into an integrated and interoperable system.’

Prof. Yaun Tseh-Lee (ICSU President), WDS-IPO inauguration

Message from the Executive Director

Establishing the International Programme Office (WDS-IPO) was certainly one of the main tasks during the 2012–13 period. As its first Executive Director, I was charged by ICSU and the WDS Scientific Committee to build a team to support the activities of this ambitious programme. Thanks to the generous support from the Japanese government through its National Institute of Information and Communications Technology, the WDS-IPO was successfully inaugurated and fully staffed.

Since then, we have been busy building strong foundations to support the future expansion and development of ICSU-WDS. Because our Members are unambiguously the pillars upholding the goals of long-term stewardship and provision of quality-assessed data and services, strengthening the membership of WDS under the guidance of its Scientific Committee was declared a strategic priority and acted upon accordingly. Going beyond recruitment, listening to our Members to better shape the future ICSU-WDS was also an important facet of this inaugural year; a task that the WDS-IPO has initiated and will maintain over the coming years.

An essential mission of ICSU-WDS is to build strong links with ICSU-sponsored research programmes and their data activities. Therefore, the WDS-IPO also concentrated on reaching out to our stakeholders through several events organized at conferences dealing, in particular, with the Future Earth Programme and global sustainability issues.

Finally, and building on the historic decision to merge WDS and CODATA Conferences, the WDS-IPO will vigorously work towards making SciDataCon a major international scientific data event and an instrument to better serve the scientific community.

Message from the Chair

The ICSU World Data System (ICSU-WDS) has a very different complexion today than it had at the 30th ICSU General Assembly (Rome; 2011). It has grown rapidly, and has now reached 'critical mass', with 68 Member Organizations headquartered in 20 countries worldwide (as of 31 March 2013). It reflects more closely the broad range of disciplines found in the Earth Sciences and Astronomy. With strong encouragement from ICSU, WDS has recruited new members in the Social Sciences, Humanities, and forged budding links with data organizations in the Health Sciences. WDS Members now contribute to the global effort through working groups that address specific issues.

The timing is very auspicious: we live and work in the era of 'open access' and 'Big Data', and international data-oriented initiatives are blossoming (e.g., GEO/GEOSS, RDA, etc.). WDS and its sister organization CODATA are joining forces to collaborate with such efforts.

From its inception, WDS was conceived by its Scientific Committee as a 'system of data systems'. With the increasing diversity of our Members, this concept is evermore important today. Global high-bandwidth networks open new options: no longer must datasets be duplicated at many nodes; server and client nodes can in fact be vastly different in scope and usage, and may not necessarily curate vast data holdings; and services are delivered online, in near-real time. Imparting sufficient flexibility and adaptability to the overall system in order to accommodate such overwhelming evolutionary forces is an overarching challenge faced by the WDS-SC and the WDS International Programme Office.

Activities in Priority Areas

Community Building

WDS Services

Strengthening Links with Partners

Capacity Building: ICSU Grant for WDS Project in Africa

Community building

Member Organizations of the ICSU World Data System (ICSU-WDS) from wide-ranging fields are the building blocks of a worldwide 'community of excellence' for scientific data. Not only do these Members participate in advancing WDS goals; their data holdings, services, and products are the cornerstone of the federated data system.

On 31 March 2013, ICSU-WDS had **68 Member Organizations** in four different categories.

47 Regular Members: Organizations that deal directly with data curation and data analysis services.

7 Network Members: Umbrella organizations representing groups of data centres and/or data services, some of which may or may not be WDS Regular Members. Usually serve as coordinating agents for nodes that have common characteristics and mostly common disciplines.

2 Partner Members: Organizations that do not deal directly with the practical details of data collection, curation, and distribution, but that contribute funding or other support to ICSU-WDS.

12 Associate Members: Organizations that are interested in the WDS endeavour and participating in our discussions, but that do not contribute direct funding or other material support. Organizations are formally accepted into ICSU-WDS by the

WDS Scientific Committee (WDS-SC), who safeguard the trustworthiness of ICSU-WDS by certifying Regular and Network Members according to internationally recognized standards (Partners and Associates are co-opted).

It is also the responsibility of the WDS-SC to develop and prioritize plans for ICSU-WDS to achieve its objectives. In particular, for ICSU-WDS to significantly contribute to projects such as the ICSU-sponsored Future Earth programme, which attempts to answer the grand challenges for global sustainability, the WDS-SC identified the following priority areas at its 7th Meeting on 1–2 November 2012 in Taipei:

1. Network building: both the targeted recruitment of Network Members and the creation of collaborative networks where these currently do not exist.
2. Expansion of the WDS disciplinary and geographic base: recruitment of WDS Members (especially Network Members) in under-represented disciplines and geographic regions.

The achievements of this focussed strategy can be witnessed in the certification of not only the first WDS Regular and Network Members from the Social Sciences and Humanities—The Language Archive and the Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure, respectively—but also the first WDS Regular Member from Africa: DataFirst, which is hosted by the University of Cape Town and promotes the long-term preservation and reuse of data from African socioeconomic surveys.

In fact, 2012–2013 also saw the affiliation of the following high-profile WDS Network Members:

- International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA)
- United States National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Earth Science Data and Information System (ESDIS) Project

Summary of survey results

- 97% of respondents concurred with the Action Items.
- 100% thought that the WDS 'community building' strategy was correct, but suggested collaboration with other organizations.
- Two-thirds were interested in joining proposed WDS Working Groups. There was a concern about repetition of previous work.
- 94% were in favour of a joint WDS–CODATA Conference, although expressed worry about ICSU-WDS maintaining its identity.
- Over 60% were keen to attend a WDS Workshop in 2013.
- 84% thought that WDS Bylaws are necessary.
- 91% agreed that WDS Members and relevant external experts should be called upon to review applicants.

- International Space Environment Service (ISES)

These networks have pledged to promote long-term data stewardship by encouraging data centres under their umbrellas to become accredited WDS Regular Members. By 31 March 2013, ICSU-WDS boasted four NASA Distributed Active Archive Centers, three ISES members, and two IVOA data centres amongst its membership; with a number of other nodes of these three networks in the application process.

In contrast, the International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange (IODE; the first WDS Network Member) has successfully established a certification procedure aligned with that used by ICSU-WDS for Regular Members. With Mustapha Mokrane (Executive Director) and Rorie Edmunds (Programme Officer) of the WDS International Programme office (WDS-IPO) in attendance, IODE member states formally agreed—at their XXII Session (11–15 March 2013; Ensenada, Mexico)—to adopt a WDS-aligned Quality Management Framework to accredit their National Oceanographic Data Centres. This followed close collaboration between the WDS-SC 'Membership and Accreditation Subcommittee' and the IODE Project Office.

Survey of WDS Members

In January 2013, the WDS-IPO contacted all current WDS Members, plus a number of candidates close to completing the application process, to gauge their thoughts on the Action Items proposed during the 7th Meeting of the WDS-SC. Thirty-two representatives of (potential) WDS Member Organizations provided their valuable contributions to an online survey. After reviewing the results, the WDS-SC requested that an overview—outlining both positive and negative findings—be made publically available.

WDS Services

At its 7th Meeting (1–2 November 2012; Taipei), the WDS Scientific Committee took the historic decision to realize two leading-edge WDS services considered to add value to the wider scientific community:

- A community-based Data Publication and Curation Service
- A searchable WDS Scalable Knowledge Network built upon an Open Metadata Catalogue

After polling WDS Members thoughts on these services—and asking for volunteers in their accomplishment—two WDS Working Groups (WDS-WGs) charged with the task of delivering these services were established.

Data Publication and Curation Service

Background

Whilst recent rapid technical developments require new approaches to ensure availability and usability of scientific data, existing methods have not supplied the necessary benefit to data producers. In contrast, data publication—based on new and proven technologies—provides strong incentive for scientists to share data and has positive effects on data quality. General acceptance of data publishing is not without controversy, however; and archiving and publishing procedures have to be transparent and accepted as part of science culture. Moreover, if published data are to be considered reliable, they should not only meet scientific requirements but also conform to current content and interoperability standards.

WDS-WG Objectives

- Promote and establish the data publication concept among data centres, science publishers, and bibliometric service providers.
- Establish data publishing services as part of scholarly publishing.

Deliverables

The following deliverables will be realized by associated Subgroups within the WDS-WG.

Deliverable 1: Generic workflow models for data publication.

Deliverable 2: Recommendations for data publishers & science publishers.

Deliverable 3 Infrastructure and organization for a one-for-all cross-referencing service for science publishers and providers of bibliometric services.

Deliverable 4: Recommendations for funding organizations.

RDA–WDS Interest Group on Publishing Data

At the First Plenary of the Research Data Alliance (RDA)—its launch event—held on 18–20 March 2013 in Gothenburg, Sweden; an RDA–WDS Interest Group on Publishing Data was initiated. This Interest Group builds on the existing framework of the WDS-WG on Data Publication, and the Subgroups within the existing WDS-WG will each seek to gain formal RDA Working Group endorsement in 2013. Other, joint RDA–WDS WGs may be created also under the umbrella of the RDA–WDS Interest Group on Publishing Data.

WDS Open Metadata Catalogue and Scalable Knowledge Network

Background

By cataloguing the data of accredited data centres/services, enriching these data with additional information, and making the results openly discoverable electronically, ICSU-WDS can become the lead resource on global capability with respect to scientific data-providing entities. Such a WDS Knowledge Network would provide a powerful tool for stakeholders to map the landscape of multidisciplinary data suppliers, and thus help identify datasets, gaps in information provision, and potential collaborative partners (for example). Furthermore, the Network would reduce global duplication of data management and sharing efforts; hence improving the cost-effectiveness of science funding programmes.

Objectives

- Establish the requirements and specifications for the WDS Metadata Catalogue and Knowledge Network and develop the strategy for their implementation.
- Look for content synergies between the Knowledge Network and (1) the Member accreditation system hosted by the WDS International Programme Office (WDS-IPO), and (2) the WDS Metadata Catalogue.
- Identify sources of data centre/service information that can be readily used to seed the Network.
- Conduct a bounded pilot-project to experiment with different linked data approaches for knowledge representation and discovery in the network.
- Advise on appropriate standards and technology choices.

Deliverables

Deliverables 1 & 2: Concept white paper, and standards and technologies guidelines.

Deliverables 3 & 4: Platforms for Metadata Catalogue and Knowledge Network deployment.

Deliverables 5 & 6: Metadata Catalogue and pilot Knowledge Network implementations.

WDS Knowledge Network Concept

A Knowledge Network is a Web-based, interlinked repository of relationships between the actors and entities that make up our research landscape: people, institutions, projects, and so on. The WDS Knowledge Network will be constructed mainly from both the parallel-developed WDS Metadata Catalogue and the WDS-IPO's membership database. These WDS resources will be integrated with existing Linked Open Data repositories—stores containing specific concepts that can be denoted by unique resource identifiers, and referenced and inspected through a Hypertext Transfer Protocol request. The information held within the WDS Metadata Catalogue and WDS membership database can be then supplemented over time using other data sources (e.g., social networks, and volunteered or crowd-sourced information). Thus, ICSU-WDS will provide an increasingly comprehensive view of the scientific topography, adding significant value for Members and stakeholders alike.

Strengthening Links with Partners

ICSU Committee on Data for Science and Technology (CODATA)

CODATA is a sister organization of WDS under ICSU, and is primarily concerned with data management. ICSU-WDS and CODATA have historically strong links due to their complementary remits, and such links have been fortified by WDS participation in past CODATA International Conferences. CODATA 23 (28–31 October 2012; Taipei) was no exception to this, with ICSU-WDS co-organizing three sessions related to data publication, as well as conducting two business meetings—including a well-attended WDS Members' Forum. Our appreciation goes out to the CODATA organizing committee and Academia Sinica for hosting us during these events. With overlapping audiences, ICSU-WDS and CODATA will hold a single co-located conference from 2014 to reinforce their ties and create the world's principal scientific data event.

Group on Earth Observation (GEO)

At the GEO-IX Plenary (22–23 June; Foz do Iguaçu, Brazil), ICSU-WDS was recognized as a Participating Organization of GEO. The WDS Open Metadata Catalogue will provide a unique aggregated metadata entry point to contribute to the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS). ICSU-WDS also co-sponsored the 2nd GEOSS Science and Technology Stakeholder Workshop—*GEOSS: Supporting Science for the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and Beyond* (28–31 August 2012; Bonn, Germany). This workshop reviewed the research topics to be addressed in order to realize the MDGs and the Earth observations needed to facilitate that research.

Future Earth: Data Challenges for Global Sustainability

In unison with the emerging 'Future Earth' project—a 10-year international research initiative that builds on the successes of existing global environmental change programmes—ICSU-WDS and CODATA have co-organized the following sessions focussing on data issues in global sustainability research.

- *Data Challenges for Global Sustainability*, Planet under Pressure 2012 Conference (27 March 2012; London, United Kingdom): Mitigating the impacts of global change requires shared access to high-quality, relevant, and readily understandable data and information about the Earth system.
- *Sharing and Stewardship of Scientific Data for Improved Decision Making and Sustainable Development. Why share data fully and openly?* Rio+20 Forum on Science, Technology and Innovation for Sustainable Development (14 June 2012; Rio de Janeiro, Brazil).
- *Future Earth Data Management*, Future Earth Stakeholders' Workshop (29 November 2012; Paris, France): Participants were invited to discuss data management arrangements proposed in the draft institutional and research framework of Future Earth and provide feedback to its Transition Team.

Research Data Alliance: RDA

The newly formed RDA has the goal of worldwide acceleration of data-driven innovation through sharing and exchange of research data. RDA was officially launched at its First Plenary (18–20 March 2013; Gothenburg, Sweden) by sponsors from the European Commission, the United States Government, the Australian Government, and leaders in the data community.

In a move to build collaboration with RDA and to strengthen its current activities, ICSU-WDS initiated discussions with RDA at its First Plenary towards establishing two RDA-WDS Interest Groups: one on 'Publishing Data' and another on 'Certification of Digital Repositories'. Other areas of collaboration were also identified.

Capacity Building

ICSU Grant for WDS project in Africa

WDS was awarded a €30,000 grant by the International Council for Science (ICSU) with the aim of creating a 'proof of concept' for a Network Data Centre for Socioeconomic Data in Africa. This project is supported by the National Research Foundation in South Africa, the ICSU Regional Office for Africa, DataFirst, and the Centre for High Performance Computing, which is funded by the Department of Science and Technology in South Africa.

The Centre will provide standardized access to a variety of data collections held by members of the network in the fields of Social, Human Activity, and Economic Sciences in Africa, and will serve as a conduit between ICSU-WDS and the contributing organizations. The project will be a success only if the governance, policy, and procedural framework to support multi-national, multi-institutional collaboration can be determined. The proof of concept, in addition to its technical objectives, has a major responsibility to define this framework.

Administration & Governance

International Programme Office Inauguration

Scientific Committee Meetings

Financial Summary

Scientific Committee

International Programme Office

WDS Members

International Programme Office Inauguration

The ICSU World Data System (ICSU-WDS) opened its new International Programme Office (WDS-IPO) at an official ceremony on 9 May 2012 in Tokyo, Japan, in the presence of the Hon. Tatsuo Kawabata (Japanese Minister for Internal Affairs and Communications) and Prof. Yuan Tseh-Lee (President of the International Council for Science [ICSU]).

The WDS-IPO will be hosted until March 2016 by the National Institute of Information and Communications Technology (NICT), and Dr. Hideo Miyahara (President of NICT) was in attendance, as well as other dignitaries including the Hon. Mieko Kamimoto (Vice-minister of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology), Dr. Takashi Onishi (President of the Science Council of Japan), and Dr. Steven Wilson (Executive Director of ICSU).

When giving his address, Prof. Lee observed that 'Society was increasingly calling on science to help solve highly complex and interconnected problems like climate change and sustainable development. However, this required that science itself, including data, become more integrated and global.' He also added that '[The World Data System] vision is to transform today's collection of data bodies into an integrated and interoperable system.'

Scientific Committee Meetings

The WDS Scientific Committee (WDS-SC) met twice in 2012. The original Committee members, whose terms ended in June 2012, convened for the final occasion on 28–30 March 2012. This meeting was held in London, United Kingdom (UK)—kindly hosted by The Royal Society (UK National Member for the International Council for Science [ICSU])—to take advantage of not only ICSU-WDS participation in the ‘Planet under Pressure 2012 Conference’ but also the opportunity to interact with UK-based WDS Members and stakeholders prior to the meeting.

The second WDS-SC Meeting was held on 1–2 November 2012 in Taipei, and brought together the newly appointed members of WDS-SC for the first time. The principal

objective of this meeting was to develop the framework that will position ICSU-WDS as the *premium global multidisciplinary network for quality-assessed scientific data*, and thus enable WDS Members to significantly contribute to projects such as Future Earth, ICSU’s flagship programme. During the course of the meeting, the WDS-SC highlighted three priority areas as being imperative to accomplishing that goal: community building, establishing relevant tools, and strengthening links with partners.

Financial Summary

The main source of income for financing the WDS International Programme Office (WDS-IPO) and its activities comes from the contributions of the National Institute of Information and Communications Technology (NICT), the WDS-IPO host organization. In addition, the International Council for Science (ICSU) supports the costs incurred for one of the WDS Scientific Committee's biannual meetings. This meeting is typically held at the ICSU Secretariat in Paris, France.

Statement of income and expenditure

The accounts of the WDS-IPO are maintained and audited by NICT, its host institute. The following statement of income and expenditure is for the period 1 April 2012 to 31 March 2013; corresponding to the Japanese fiscal year (FY) 2012.

Income	Japanese Yen
2012 Contribution from NICT	31,000,000¥
Carryover from FY2011	10,000,000¥
Grant from ICSU	3,000,000¥
Total income	44,000,000¥

Expenditure	Japanese Yen
Communication and Promotion	15,101,518¥
Administrative Support	10,763,088¥
Other Projects and Activities (Network Data Centre for Socioeconomic Data in Africa)	3,000,000¥
Travel and Meeting Costs	6,402,498¥
Other Costs (Insurance, Bank Charges, etc.)	741,555¥
Equipment	1,196,448¥
Total Expenditure	37,205,107¥
Net (Income - Expenditure)	6,794,893¥

Scientific Committee

ICSU-WDS is governed by a Scientific Committee composed of prominent scientists actively involved in Data/Computer Sciences, and dealing with large dataset issues and long-term data stewardship. The WDS-SC includes directors of WDS Member Organizations and covers a broad range of disciplines and geographical areas. The Terms of Reference of the WDS-SC are defined within the WDS Constitution as approved by the Executive Board of the International Council for Science (ICSU-EB) in April 2012.

The second Scientific Committee was appointed in June 2012 by the ICSU-EB. In the interests of both continuity and renewal, the ICSU-EB invited half of the previous WDS-SC to serve a second three-year term (2012–2015), while replacing the remainder with others who might bring fresh insights to ICSU-WDS. On an exceptional basis, the ICSU-EB also established a thirteenth seat for a Health Sciences data expert in response to ICSU's research priorities.

Chair

Jean-Bernard Minster: Scripps Institute of Oceanography, University of California, United States of America (USA)

Vice-chairs

Michael Diepenbroek: Institute for Marine Environmental Sciences, University of Bremen, Germany

Françoise Genova: Centre de Données Astronomiques de Strasbourg, France

Ex Officio Members

Howard Moore: ICSU Secretariat, France

Yasuhiro Murayama: National Institute of Information and Communications Technology, Japan

Members

Claudia Emerson: Sandra Rotman Centre, University Health Network / University of Toronto, Canada

Kim Finney: Australian Antarctic Data Centre, Australia

Wim Hugo: South African Earth Observation System, South Africa

Jane Hunter: School of Information Technology and Electrical Engineering, University of Queensland, Australia

Vasily Kopylov: All-Russian Research Institute of Hydrometeorological Information–World Data Centre, Russian Federation

Guoqing Li: Centre for Earth Observation and Digital Earth, People's Republic of China

Ruth E. Neilan: Central Bureau of the International Global Navigation Satellite System Service, USA

Lesley Rickards: Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level, National Oceanography Centre, United Kingdom

Ryosuke Shibasaki: Center for Spatial Information Science, University of Tokyo, Japan

Ariel Troisi: *Oceanography Department, Naval Hydrographic Office, Ministry of Defence, Argentina*

International Programme Office

The International Programme Office acts under the leadership of the WDS Executive Director with guidance from the WDS Scientific Committee (WDS-SC). It is supported by a Programme Officer (since 1 August 2012) and an Administrative Officer (since 1 September 2012). A Senior Advisor was additionally appointed to the WDS-IPO by the International Council for Science (ICSU). It is the responsibility of the WDS-IPO to coordinate the daily

operations of ICSU-WDS and implement the decisions of the WDS-SC. Moreover, the WDS-IPO organizes the twice-yearly meetings of the WDS-SC and the biennial WDS Conference, as well as conducting outreach and promotional activities. Following an agreement with ICSU, the WDS-IPO will be hosted and financially supported until 31 March 2016 by the National Institute of Information and Communications Technology in Tokyo, Japan.

Staff

Executive Director: Mustapha Mokrane

Senior Advisor: Takashi Watanabe

Programme Officer: Rorie Edmunds

Administrative Officer: Yuko Nikaïdo

WDS Members

On 31 March 2013, the ICSU World Data System had **68 Member Organizations** in four different categories.

Regular Members

Organization Name	Host Institution(s)	Country
Australian Antarctic Data Centre	Australian Government, Antarctic Division	Australia
Australian Bureau of Meteorology	Australian Government	Australia
Centre de Données Astronomiques de Strasbourg	University of Strasbourg / Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)	France
Chinese Astronomical Data Center	Chinese National Astronomical Observatory, Ministry of Science and Technology / Chinese Academy of Sciences	People's Republic of China (PRC)
Crustal Dynamics Data Information System	United States National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Godard Space Flight Center (GSFC)	United States of America (USA)
Data Centre for Geography, Moscow	Lomonosov Moscow State University, Faculty of Geography	Russian Federation
DataFirst	University of Cape Town	South Africa
Deutsche Klimarechenzentrum–WDC Climate	Max Planck Institute for Meteorology / German Climate Computing Centre	Germany
Fish Database of Taiwan (Academia Sinica, Taiwan)	Biodiversity Research Center	China–Taipei
Flanders Marine Institute, Data Centre	Flanders Marine Institute	Belgium
Goddard Earth Sciences Data and Information Services Center	NASA GSFC	USA
Incorporated Institutions for Research in Seismology, Data Management System	National Science Foundation	USA
Integrated Earth Data Applications	Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory of Columbia University.	USA
International Earth Rotation and Reference Systems	Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy, Germany	Germany
International Global Navigation Satellite System Service	NASA	USA
International Service of Geomagnetic Indices	LATMOS (CNRS, University of Versailles Saint Quentin, University of Pierre et Marie Curie)	France
International Soil Reference and Information Centre (ISRIC)–WDC Soils	ISRIC–World Soil Information	Netherlands
National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC) Distributed Active Archive Center (DAAC)	University of Colorado	USA
Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) DAAC	ORNL	USA
Paleoclimatology Branch, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's (NOAA's) National Climatic Data Center (NCDC)	NOAA	USA
PANGAEA–Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science	Center for Marine Environmental Sciences, University of Bremen	Germany
The Language Archive	Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics	Netherlands
Tropical Ecology Assessment and Monitoring Initiative	Conservation International	USA

Ukrainian Geospatial Data Center	Space Research Institute of Ukraine	Ukraine
WDC–Colorado University	NSIDC, University of Colorado	USA
WDC–Earth Resources Observation and Science (EROS)	EROS Center, U.S. Geological Survey	USA
WDC–Geoinformatics and Sustainable Development	National Technical University of Ukraine	Ukraine
WDC–Geomagnetism, Copenhagen	National Space Institute	Denmark
WDC–Geomagnetism, Edinburgh	British Geological Survey	United Kingdom (UK)
WDC–Geomagnetism, Kyoto	Data Analysis Center for Geomagnetism and Space Magnetism, Kyoto University	Japan
WDC–Ionosphere and Space Weather	National Institute of Information and Communications Technology	Japan
WDC–Meteorology, Asheville	NCDC, NOAA	USA
WDC–Meteorology, Obninsk	All-Russian Research Institute of Hydrometeorological Information–World Data Centre (RIHMI-WDC)	Russian Federation
WDC–Oceanography, Obninsk	RIHMI-WDC	Russian Federation
WDC–Oceanography, Silver Spring	National Oceanographic Data Center, NOAA	USA
WDC–Oceanography, Tianjin	National Marine Data and Information Service	PRC
WDC–Remote Sensing of the Atmosphere	German Aerospace Center	Germany
WDC–Renewable Resources and Environment	Institute of Geography Sciences and Natural Resource Research, CAS	PRC
WDC–Rockets, Satellites and Earth Rotation	RIHMI-WDC	Russian Federation
WDC–Solar Activity (Base de Données Solaire Sol 2000)	Laboratoire d'Études Spatiales et d'Instrumentation en Astrophysique, Observatoire de Paris	France
WDC–Solar Terrestrial Physics, Moscow	Geophysical Center, Russian Academy of Sciences (RAS)	Russian Federation
WDC–Solid Earth Physics, Moscow	Geophysical Center, RAS	Russian Federation
WDC–Sunspot Index and Long-term Solar Observations	Solar Influences Data analysis Center–Royal Observatory of Belgium	Belgium
World Federation for Culture Collections (WFCC)–World Data Centre for Microorganisms	WFCC	PRC
World Data Service for Geophysics	National Geophysical Data Center, NOAA	USA
World Glacier Monitoring Service, Zurich	University of Zurich	Switzerland
World Stress Map Project	German Research Centre for Geosciences, World Stress Map Project, Helmholtz Centre Potsdam	Germany

Network Members

Organization Name	Host Institution(s)	Country of Secretariat
Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure– European Research Infrastructure Consortium		Netherlands
International Laser Ranging Service	NASA	USA
International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization / Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission	Belgium
International Space Environment Service	International Astronomical Union, International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics, and International Union for Radio Science	Canada
International Virtual Observatory Alliance		France
International VLBI Service for Geodesy and Astrometry	NASA	USA
NASA Earth Science Data and Information System Project	NASA	USA

Partner Members

International Environmental Data Rescue Organization		USA
International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics		Germany

Associate Members

Committee on Electronic Information and Communication	International Mathematical Union	USA
Datta Meghe Institute Of Medical Sciences	Deemed University	India
Elsevier		Netherlands
French Academy of Sciences		France
International Association of Hydrological Sciences		France
International Association of Scientific, Technical & Medical Publishers		Netherlands
International Commission for Acoustics		Australia
International Union of Geological Sciences		USA
John Wiley & Sons Ltd		UK
Korea Institute of Science and Technology Information		Republic of Korea
The Royal Society of New Zealand		New Zealand
WorldWideScience Alliance	U.S. Department of Energy Office of Scientific and Technical Information	USA

Credits:

Test tubes ©haydenbird, Passenger and iceberg
©thp73, Colorful fishing action in West africa ©Peeter Viisimaa, Circuit
board ©ArtyFree, Molecular Structure ©nicolas_, XL satellite dish twilight ©Estate of
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